

LANGUAGE INTERFERENCE AND CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS HYPOTHESIS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922741>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 7th October 2024

Accepted: 9th October 2024

Published: 12th October 2024

KEYWORDS

interlingual interference, intralingual interference, transference, foreign language teaching.

ABSTRACT

This study is devoted to the concepts of interference and transference in the linguodidactic aspect. In the first part of the work, the author examines the main manifestations of interlingual and intralingual interference at different language levels, analyzes the opinions of methodologists on this issue.

INTRODUCTION

When learning a foreign language, students may encounter various psycholinguistic phenomena. Some of them create difficulties in learning a foreign language, while others, on the contrary, simplify this process. This study is devoted to the phenomena of language interference and transference, as well as their role in the process of learning a foreign language. The relevance of the work is due to the fact that at the moment in the methodology of teaching foreign languages there is no single point of view on the linguodidactic potential of interference and transference, while the very question of the functioning of these phenomena remains complex and difficult.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concept of "language interference" has become widespread in linguistic science thanks to the fundamental work of the scientist W. Weinreich "Language Contacts". In this work, W. Weinreich defined the term "interference" as "instances of deviation from linguistic norms that occur in the speech of bilinguals due to their proficiency in several languages". This linguist was also the first to propose a classification of interference and identified phonetic, lexical, and grammatical interference. This classification reflects the types of interlingual interference, that is, transfer, in which the interaction of several language systems occurs in the mind of a bilingual.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the most common types of *interlingual interference* is phonetic interference. As a rule, it manifests itself in prosody and at the segmental level through the replacement of phonemes of one language with phonemes of another [1]. Interlingual phonetic interference is considered a significant obstacle for learners in the process of learning a foreign language, and therefore should be leveled through a comparative analysis of the systems of the contacting languages [2]. In our work, we also share this point of view. To overcome this type of interference, various exercises in sound differentiation are most often offered,

allowing learners to compare the pronunciation and sound of English and Russian phonemes and, as a result, overcome the influence of interference [3].

Interlingual grammatical interference is associated with the disruption of the grammatical structure of one language under the influence of another. This phenomenon is common both at the word level and at the levels of phrases and sentences: learners' errors manifest themselves in the addition of extra morphemes, substitution of case meanings, and incorrect word order in a sentence. It should be noted that errors caused by interlingual grammatical interference should be leveled through a comparative analysis of the systems of two contacting languages [2].

Later, the term intralingual interference entered linguistic science. This phenomenon is defined as an occurrence that occurs within the system of one language studied by an individual due to contact of a linguistic form with recently acquired linguistic units [3]. The phenomenon of intralingual interference remains complex and poorly studied: at this stage, there is no consensus on the causes of intralingual interference. On the one hand, interference of this type is determined by the nature of the language being studied, its structure, and the presence of linguistic units similar in form and meaning. On the other hand, the very process of learning a foreign language in some way provokes the emergence of intra-linguistic interference, since often the skills of using certain linguistic units already formed by learners inhibit the process of forming new skills [1].

Due to the complexity of the phenomenon of intra-linguistic interference, various classifications of its manifestations are proposed. For example, according to J. Richards, a famous scientist who devoted himself to the theory of teaching English, intra-linguistic interference can manifest itself as:

- 1) overgeneralization, in which learners generalize previously learned rules and go beyond their boundaries, since they mistakenly identify some linguistic phenomena with each other (for example, using "oxes" instead of oxen);
- 2) incomplete application of the rule, which is expressed in the fact that students in their speech take into account only part of the restrictions reflected in the recently learned rule (for example, in accordance with the rule, they decide to use the initial form of the verb in a general question in the simple present tense in English, but mistakenly retain the ending -s in the negation);
- 3) ignoring the restrictions on the application of a certain rule, manifested in the use of the rule in situations to which it does not apply (for example, students use who with inanimate objects);
- 4) the consequence of students overcoming communication difficulties (for example, wanting to describe fireworks, a student uses the incorrect phrase "fire flowers" instead of the lexeme fireworks);
- 5) the formation of erroneous hypotheses regarding the linguistic phenomena being studied, associated with the fact that students incorrectly perceive certain characteristics inherent in linguistic phenomena (for example, a student identifies the form was exclusively as a marker of the simple past tense, and subsequently incorrectly uses the tense form in the sentence: "He was doing some exercises");
- 6) errors caused by teaching, arising as a result of the teacher unintentionally causing a confusion of two or more linguistic phenomena in the minds of students (for example, the teacher uses indirect questions in his speech, characterized by direct word order, and the students incorrectly recognize this linguistic phenomenon, starting to use the same word order in a direct question) [3]. There are classifications of intralingual interference on other grounds. For example, the linguist S. P. Rozanova, analyzing the phenomenon of intralingual interference, identifies two of its most important manifestations: contamination and paraphasia [4]. By contamination, the author understands the erroneous formation of a new word form by combining two linguistic elements. For example, a learner may unconsciously

“combine” elements of two similar expressions “to speak about something” and “to say something about”, resulting in the incorrect statement “My mother said about it”. The term “paraphasia” is defined by S.P. Rozanova as “the erroneous use of one lexeme instead of another within the same foreign language” [2]. In turn, paraphasia may be formal (due to the external or sound similarity of word forms), formal-substantive (with partial coincidence of the form and meaning of word forms), substantive (with coincidence of the meanings of word forms). Examples of formal paraphasia include the interchange of linguistic units winter, windy, window; their, there, they’re; quite and quiet, weather and whether. Manifestations of formal-substantive paraphasia are considered to be errors in the use of cognate words with different prefixes, for example, to undo, to overdo, to redo; to reuse and to overuse. Violations of norms caused by formal paraphasia can be observed when students interchange lexemes belonging to the same semantic series: to speak, to say, to tell; to watch, to look, to see; to make and to do. According to a number of scientists, errors caused by different manifestations of intralingual interference should also be corrected with the help of contrastive exercises, differentiation exercises, translation exercises (from a foreign language to a native language and vice versa) [3].

Thus, we have considered the phenomena of interlingual and intralingual interference in the study of a foreign language and analyzed the main existing classifications of these phenomena. We emphasize that traditionally, in the methods of teaching foreign languages, it is proposed to prevent and neutralize the influence of both interlingual and intralingual interference through various exercises. However, we also think it is important that in recent studies, methodologists and linguists treat errors caused by interference more leniently. Thus, some scientists emphasize that the study of interlingual interference exclusively as negative transfer is one-sided, since it “takes into account only the specifics of the native language and its influence on the studied foreign language”. This position leads to a rethinking of the phenomenon of interference: it can be considered to be bidirectional, reflecting the specificity of the primary and secondary language systems [3]. In this paper, we also adhere to a similar opinion and propose, on the one hand, to prevent and neutralize language interference in situations in which it complicates communication; on the other hand, it seems to us possible to use the linguodidactic potential of interference. To this end, students can master particularly complex phenomena of contacting languages in comparison with each other, as well as analyze the mistakes they have made previously. In our opinion, these actions will not only allow students to neutralize the influence of interference, but will also ensure a targeted perception and comprehension of the linguistic phenomena being studied.

CONCLUSION

Thus, in this article we have considered the concepts of interference and transference, analyzed the role of these phenomena in the process of learning a foreign language. In our opinion, both of these phenomena have linguodidactic potential. Thus, the phenomenon of linguistic interference complicates the process of mastering a foreign language and needs to be prevented and overcome. At the same time, the process of leveling the influence of interference, which consists mainly in comparing the systems of contacting phenomena, is extremely effective for the formation of linguistic competence of students, for the automation and consolidation of existing skills. Unlike interference, the phenomenon of transference has a more positive effect on the process of learning a foreign language, while the frequency of positive transfer depends on both the students and the teacher.

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